

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE NURSE'S WORK IN CARDIOLOGY PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

Patients with myocardial infarction need continuous monitoring and expensive and advanced medical examinations. In order to adequately respond to the dynamically changing health needs of patients, nurses must provide a new quality type of health care, expand nursing functions, train nurses in innovations in the profession, and find new approaches to improve the quality of life of patients.

Keywords: myocardial infarction, patients, health care.

INTRODUCTION

Myocardial infarction is one of the most severe forms of ischemic heart disease. It is of great social importance because of the high disability and mortality it causes. The significance of the problem is primarily determined by the profound social and health needs of the patients, combined with impaired quality of life and increased specific health requirements. Health care is central to the overall treatment process of patients with myocardial infarction. Their quality largely determines the economic stability and sustainable development of healthcare institutions.

Improving the quality of modern hospital operations requires continuous monitoring of myocardial infarction patients' satisfaction with the medical services offered, meeting patients' health care needs, and planning health care. The nurse is the person who plays a key role in the highly specialized field of cardiology, providing health care to patients. She must carry out her activities at all times and in such a way as to justify the public trust, protect and enhance the prestige of the nursing profession, and above all protect the interests of individual patients. She is accountable for her unique and challenging work in cardiology practice. In the long term, this would contribute to changing the status of the chronically ill patient from a burdensome problem of society to a full subject in need of a meaningful future, dignity, protection and psycho-emotional well-being. In order to solve these problems, it is necessary to improve the quality of activity in cardiology practice, to introduce a new approach to the organization of activities performed by health care professionals in the modern hospital, and to continuously improve the qualifications of health professionals.

PURPOSE

To study and analyze the organizational problems of hospital treatment in patients with myocardial infarction and create a modern health care organization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study included nurses working in the cardiology departments of the Multiprofile Hospitals for Active Treatment of three districts of North-Western Bulgaria: Hospital - Vratsa, Hospital - Montana and Hospital - Vidin. 150 nurses were surveyed by direct

anonymous questionnaire. The obtained data were processed with mathematical and statistical methods. Tables and graphs were made using WORD and EXCEL programs.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The nurses surveyed caring for patients with myocardial infarction were aged from 30 to 70 years. The relative share of health care professionals between the ages of 55 and 65 is the largest, 47.0%, and those between the ages of 40 and 54 years, 29.0%. The relative proportion of nurses under 40 years of age was 25.0%, and their average level of work experience in cardiology departments was 10 years. This indicates experience in health care of patients with myocardial infarction.

The job description is a document that regulates the functions and duties, rights and responsibilities of nurses related to the effective performance of their duties. An analysis of the current job descriptions informs us that they reflect only the activities that the nurse performs independently and under the doctor's direction, related to the provision of medical and health care and the performance of manipulations. Missing are nursing activities that are essential for patients with myocardial infarction, such as: preventing complications and counselling patients and their relatives; assessing health needs and counselling individuals with increased health risks; drawing up a nursing care plan and incorporating the nursing process; and assisting individuals for their resocialization.

More than half of the surveyed nurses working in cardiology departments (70.0%) thought that the activities regulated in the job description were sufficient in scope. Depending on the work experience, it is noticeable that nurses who think that the activities in the job description are not sufficient in volume have the least work experience (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Relationship between nurses' work experience and their opinion on the volume of the regulated activities in the job description

Although the majority of nurses felt that the activities regulated by the job description were sufficient in scope, 61.0% reported that it was common to perform activities outside those specified in the job description. Nurses most often have to work with documentation - 31.8%, perform nursing manipulations - 34.2%, measure somatic indicators - 20.1%, work with a computer outside of the duties - 5.6%, educate patients - 8.3% and others.

In the process of communication and joint activity of people, contradictions and conflicts may arise. The

nurse is the professional who can identify the presence of problems, as the closest participant in the healing process, choose the appropriate form and time to overcome them.

Respondent nurses in cardiology departments most often encounter problems with the provision of materials and supplies - 37.2%, second place but not in importance - 22.0% - the communication. No less in importance were organizational problems - 21.1% and health promotion problems - 19.7% (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Distribution of problems in the activity of nurses

It is evident that 1/3 of the nurses surveyed identified workplace problems as significant.

The specificity of medical assistance and health care delivery requires medical professionals and patients to work together in the patient's interest. Nurses with their professionalism definitely have a significant

role in the adaptation of patients to the new way of life. This is what the results of the study show. More than half (60.0%) of the nurses said that patients seek their professional opinion about illness-related care, 36.1% thought that only sometimes and 3.9% of them answered negatively (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Distribution of nurses according to patients' interest in health care

The path to good patient relations begins with the formation of a positive attitude, which is achieved through professional communication and interaction skills. Through interpersonal interaction, the nurse is able to most fully meet the needs of patients and fulfil

their professional obligations. The willingness to communicate with the patient creates an atmosphere for learning and disseminating information, but due to the expanded scope of nursing functions, nursing professionals do not have enough time to communicate with patients (Figure 4).

Fig.4. Nurses' willingness to communicate with patients

The analysis of the results showed that 61.1% of the surveyed medical professionals "insufficiently" talk to patients. The responses are ranked as follows: 22.8% talk "enough" with patients, "I don't have time" to talk - 11.1%; "I don't talk" with patients - 5.0%.

The preferred form of communication in medical institutions where treatment of myocardial infarction

patients is carried out is oral. This was also revealed by the answers to the question, "Do you provide enough information about the hygiene and dietary regimen?" - 46.6% of nurses fully provide information, 35.6% of respondents partially inform patients, 13.9% of nurses provide insufficient information and 3.9% do not provide the necessary information to patients at all (Fig. 5).

Fig.5. Provision of information on hygiene and diet

Good health care management of patients with myocardial infarction prevents the progression of their complications, so it is more cost-effective to invest in awareness and education. This is a significant investment of society, which is aimed at preserving human resources and further saving material resources. With their activities, nurses would help to respond to complex emotional experiences, anxious doubts and obtaining support at a difficult and unfortunately sometimes turning point in the life of the patient and his family. In the complex approach to myocardial infarction patients, support and understanding is an important point to achieve comprehensive nursing care and improved quality of life. Myocardial infarction is not a hopeless diagnosis, but a long journey towards finding the most favorable way of living with it, in which the nurse takes an active part.

Medical professionals are concerned with the problems of patients because the foundation of the

nursing profession is respect for human rights, dedication and a sense of responsibility. Health care professionals are aware of the fact that they are the persons to whom patients can confide and share their problems, and they must justify the trust that is placed in them. This is why 42.2% of respondents reported that if they receive a complaint from a patient, they pay attention to it and try to resolve it, even if it is not directly related to their work. Another 53.9% try to solve problems that arise, but only if it is directly related to their activity. Only 3.9% of healthcare professionals do not pay attention to patient complaints. Psychosocial care, according to the surveyed nurses, plays an important role in the lives of patients (Fig. 6). As it is evident 96.6% of nurses are of this opinion, the parameters being from "yes, completely" to "yes, sometimes", ranked as follows: 77.2% - yes, completely, 19.4% - yes, sometimes and 3.3% - I cannot decide.

Fig.6. Myocardial infarction patients' need for psychosocial help and support according to nurses

In order to improve the quality of health care in medical institutions, nurses need not only appropriate training, adequate to the needs of society, but also a change in their professional career. A major means for a successful professional career is postgraduate training and specialization.

A significant proportion of nursing staff (75.6%) believe that specialized training of the nurse is necessary for working with patients with myocardial infarction, 41.5% think it is very necessary, 34.1% think it is necessary, 12.8% think it is necessary but partially. Specialized training of nurses is not necessary according to 11.6%, and there were no answers for not necessary at all (Fig. 7).

Fig.7. Nurses' need for specialized training in working with patients with myocardial infarction

When working with patients with myocardial infarction, nurses need to continuously educate, inform, update their theoretical knowledge and practical skills for the benefit of the patient. Successful professional realization and higher authority will lead to satisfaction, which will motivate nurses for future professional success, for high quality care and for taking autonomous duties and responsibilities in nursing activities for myocardial infarction patients.

CONCLUSION

The creation of a health care organization in hospital structures that meets modern requirements is impossible without the role of the nurse, who is able to meet modern challenges to public health and to assist in the implementation of activities that make the patient's life meaningful.

The nurse fulfils important roles and responsibilities in cardiology practice. She contributes to the quality care and support of patients with heart disease who often require specialized care and attention. The work of cardiology nurses plays a key role in maintaining cardiac health and improving the quality of life of patients. This reinforces the need to improve the professional qualifications of nurses and the quality of health care, meeting the health needs and improving the quality of life of patients.

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